

NOVEL POROUS WALL VASCULAR NETWORKS FOR REPEATED SELF-HEALING

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ABSTRACT

A key limitation in the vascular self-healing systems to date has been the inability to achieve repeated healing for an infinite number of cycles due to fracture of the fluid-carrying vessel, which ultimately restricts and then terminates the transportation of the healing agent throughout the structure. In order to overcome this limitation a novel concept employing a porous thermoplastic network integrated within a fibre-reinforced composite laminate has been utilised. This approach promotes adhesive failure between the network and the surrounding host matrix material, thus exposing a series of radial pores and permitting the secretion of the liquid healing agent into the damage crack plane. In this study, mechanical characterisation of the crack-vascule interaction through a fracture mechanics (Mode I) assessment of PTFE tubes embedded within a fibre reinforced composite has been undertaken and indicated that moderate crack arrest occurs at the location of each vascule resulting in a controlled fracture process; a desirable attribute for self-healing composites. On arrival of a propagating crack to the external wall of the network, adhesive failure between the epoxy matrix and circumference of the network occurs exposes the external walls of the tubes, which, when porous will allow the healing agent to permeate out into the damage area without fracture of the network. The experimental characterisation of this system is on-going with further self-healing trials imminent to determine the full potential of this approach to accomplish repeated self-healing in fibre reinforced composite laminates

1 INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced polymer composites are susceptible to many forms of damage in every-day use due to a wide range of loading conditions such as mechanical overload, fatigue, impact and heat or chemical attack, which result in cracks throughout the structure that are notoriously challenging to detect and repair. Delamination, microcracking, crack opening, shear cracking, fibre rupture, pullout and debonding are all examples of damage modes found within FRPs, indicating the wide range of complex mechanisms by which damage may occur, resulting in a reduction in mechanical performance and the increased likelihood of structural failure. Although the design of advanced composites is strength and stiffness driven, epoxy matrix composites in particular are inherently brittle and prone to matrix microcracking, and with the ever-growing desire for structures with longer lifetimes requiring less maintenance, the ability to recover fracture properties has stimulated great interest in self-healing materials [1].

At present, three main approaches to self-healing exist: microcapsules, intrinsic and vascular. Each of these differs by its means of introducing healing functionality, which consequently influences the healable damage volume, repeatability and rate of healing [1]. Although microcapsules are easy to incorporate within a polymer material and can achieve high healing efficiencies and healing rates in small to moderate damage volumes, their use is limited as fracture of the microcapsule is required during a healing event, which leads to local depletion of the healing agent and voids where it was once stored. As a result, this approach is limited locally to a single healing event as long-range transport of the healing agent is not possible [1-3]. High healing efficiencies and multiple healing cycles have been

achieved using intrinsic systems, which achieve repair through the inherent reversibility of bonding of the matrix polymer. However, healing is confined to a limited damage volume, as intrinsic rebonding requires close proximity of damaged surfaces [1].

The integration of vascular networks into materials provides an effective delivery mechanism for the healing agents to reach the damage site, allowing transportation over long distances and introducing a means by which both resin and hardener can be replenished. This approach addresses the main limitations associated with microcapsular and intrinsic systems by enabling the possibility of multiple healing cycles over greater damage volumes. A number of techniques have been used to form vasculures, including hollow glass fibres [4] and channels [5][6], which release the healing agent upon fracture. These are compatible with a wide range of healing resins and activation methods and they are easily integrated within a composite structure. However, the vasculures need to be of relatively large diameter in comparison with the reinforcement and low viscosity resin systems are necessary to allow the healing agents to infiltrate into the damage area. In addition, the vasculures must be fractured to allow the healing agents to release into the crack plane, which limits the potential of this method for repeated healing [1][7].

Several examples of studies utilising 2D and 3D networks of capillaries or channels that enable multiple cycles do exist, such as the healing of cracks in coating materials [9-11] and in skin-core debonding with foam crushing in composite sandwich structures [11-13]. Recently, Toohey et al. [11] used direct write assembly to create interpenetrating microvascular networks which independently supply two-component epoxy healing agents to the damage site to heal cracks in epoxy coatings. Autonomic curing was achieved in the crack plane after delivery for up to 30 sequential cycles, however this was ultimately limited by the inability of the resin and hardener to mix in the crack plane. A thick build-up of polymerised material directly above the channels, which increased after each cycle, most likely blocked the flow of resin to the damage site [10-11].

Williams et al. [12][13] developed a self-healing system for a composite sandwich structure subjected to impact damage. This system utilised either single or dual networks inserted in the mid-plane of the sandwich core, with vertical risers joining the network to the skin-core bond region. Post impact, the healing agents were delivered through this network to the site of damage; the single network delivered a pre-mixed solution whilst the dual networks separately delivered the resin and hardener to the disbanded interface between the foam core and FRP laminate skin. A full recovery of flexural strength and primary failure mode in a single cycle was achieved for both the single and dual networks when the vertical risers were ruptured. However, multiple healing cycles were not achieved in the sandwich panel containing dual networks due to insufficient mixing of the resin in the crack plane, and scope for improvement surrounding the likely mass penalty and reliability still remain. In addition, both the work carried out by Toohey et al. [9-11] and Williams et al. [12][13] require the cracks to be confined to the coating material or near the skin-core interface. This enables the vascular networks to be strategically placed away from sites with a high probability of failure but to terminate where damage is most likely to occur [14].

While the range of fabrication methods and materials for microvascular networks are somewhat limited, a great degree of design freedom exists in the design phase, such as choice of channel diameter, degree of branching, location of branches and channel orientation. The optimal network architecture for such systems will vary from application to application and this is a critical consideration in addition to the matrix properties, the fluids involved and the distribution methods when designing such networks. A balance between maximum efficiency of the network and minimal negative structural impact must be achieved [8].

The inclusion of vasculures in a fibre-reinforced laminate causes disruption to the fibre architecture that can consequently affect its mechanical performance. It has been determined that control of the local misalignment of fibres resulting from such inclusions is crucial when aiming to minimise the knock-on effect on mechanical performance. This is brought about by the presence of resin pockets

that can lead to high internal stress concentrations and fibre distortions such as waviness [15][16]. Norris et al. [5-7] investigated different methods for vasculature inclusion, namely by placing the vasculature in between the central plies and by cutting the central plies and placing the vasculature in the recess. It was found that for vasculature oriented transverse (90°) to the fibre direction, the first fabrication route resulted in large resin pockets and significant fibre waviness compared to the second fabrication route. Crack arrest for the second fabrication route was much lower resulting in controlled failure of the fracture plane and more reliable crack-vasculature interaction during Mode I and Mode II testing, which is ideally suited for self-healing applications.

This study utilises a novel concept employing a porous thermoplastic network integrated within fibre-reinforced composite laminates transverse to the fibre direction, to promote adhesive failure between the network and the surrounding host matrix material, thus exposing a series of radial pores and permitting the secretion of the liquid healing agent into the damage crack plane. A proof of concept study is reported herein, by which an investigation into the crack-vasculature interaction under Mode I propagation has been undertaken. This is firstly to assess the effect of including a network on the laminate properties and secondly to observe the path by which the crack propagates, which will confirm whether the chosen network will debond from the matrix, and thus be exposed – a requirement to allow the healing agent to permeate into the damage site. An additional experiment has been carried out to evaluate the compatibility of a novel healing agent/catalyst combination with this system.

2 COMPOSITE-VASCULE INTEGRATION

2.1. Vasculature Manufacture

Thermoplastic tubes were chosen to act as vasculature due to the probability that the tubes would debond from the thermoset matrix when the crack tip arrives at the vasculature during crack propagation. Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) tubing was selected due to its high melting point, which would allow it to withstand the cure cycle temperature of the laminate, and the ability to obtain in the form of a small diameter tube. Flexible tubing with an outside diameter of 0.56mm and a 0.4mm bore was sourced from Goodfellow. Pores of 200microns diameter were created in the external wall of the vasculature using focused ion beam milling (figure 1).

Figure 1 200 micron pore created using a focused ion beam

2.2. Composite Laminate Manufacture

Unidirectional (0° oriented) carbon fibre reinforced epoxy (Gurit SE70) was chosen due to the possibility of low temperature cure which is amenable to both a wide range of thermoplastic materials

and resin systems used in self-healing. 16-ply unidirectional laminates (3.2mm nominal thickness) were manufactured for fracture mechanics testing based on ASTM guidelines. All laminates were cured in an oven at 70°C for 16 hours and 1 bar pressure.

Following on from the findings discussed by Norris et al. [5-7], transverse-oriented vasculures were introduced into the laminate at 10mm intervals through cutting plies and placing in the recess in order to help promote controlled failure of the fracture plane and more reliable crack-vascure interaction. Due to the SE70 plies having a nominal thickness of 0.2mm, the central two plies were cut to allow for the 0.56mm PTFE tubing to be placed (figure 2). However, as the diameter of the tubes is slightly greater than the recess, a small degree of moulding of the plies over the tubes was expected, as the tubes print through to the surface of the laminate during lay up.

Figure 2. Schematic and micrograph of laminate-vascure fabrication method

3 FRACTURE MECHANICS TESTING

In order to assess the impact of PTFE-tube inclusion on the fracture properties of the host material and to determine how cracks interact with the vasculures, crack propagation was monitored and toughness evaluated under Mode I fracture. Three different configurations were tested; a plain laminate in order to establish the base-line material fracture properties, a laminate with an empty recess in order to determine the detrimental effect of cutting the load-bearing plies and a laminate with vasculures embedded as discussed previously to evaluate, what, if any, effect these tubes have on the propagation of cracks. The test procedures are outlined as follows.

3.1. *Mode I Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) test methodology*

Testing was based on the ASTM D5528-01 standard [17]. The samples were tested on an Instron 3343 with a 1kN load cell at a displacement rate of 2mm/min via piano hinges adhered to the end of the specimens using Redux 810 (Hexcel, UK). Both the load and displacement were recorded, and crack growth was monitored using a video camera with white marker fluid placed along the sample edge to aid visual enhancement. A PTFE film insert of 20µm thickness was inserted at the mid-plane of the laminate to act as a crack initiator (figure 3). Following this, the crack was allowed to stabilise over 35mm before arriving at the vascure, and permitted to propagate for 50mm when the test was stopped. The test set up is shown in figure 4. Five specimens were tested for each laminate configuration.

The Mode I strain energy release rate (G_I) was calculated using the modified beam theory [17]:

$$G_I = \frac{3P\delta}{2b(a + \Delta_I)}$$

where P corresponds to the applied load, δ the load point displacement, b the specimen thickness and a the delamination length. As the beam is not perfectly built-in, a correction factor Δ_I is used that

accounts for rotation that may occur at the delamination front, which would otherwise overestimate G_I , as laid out in the ASTM guidelines [17].

Figure 3 Specimen geometry for Mode I testing

Figure 4 DCB Test set up

3.2. Results and discussion

Mode I crack-vascule interaction

The fracture toughness (represented by the critical strain energy release rate) as a function of crack length for the different laminates subjected to Mode I fracture are shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Critical strain energy release rate as a function of crack length for Mode I propagating cracks

The fracture toughness for all three configurations remained similar until approximately 2mm before the first vascule where, as observed visually, the crack jumped into the vascule and a small decrease in fracture toughness was observed, possibly due to a combination of the termination of the load-bearing plies and the resin pockets present either side of the vascule, that caused a drop in load as the crack tip approaches the vascules, in line with findings from Norris et al. [6]. The toughness was then seen to increase over the baseline at the location of the vascules, which act to arrest the cracks and prevent them from propagating for a period of time. Once the strain energy was great enough, the crack then rapidly propagated around the vascule and a decrease in fracture toughness was once again seen. As the crack moves away from the midplane after the first vascule, as shown in figure 5, it is impossible to guarantee that pure Mode I fracture is occurring. This is a result of the structural coupling that may exist in the asymmetric sublaminates formed as the delamination grows. In addition to this, anticlastic bending effects may also result, which can cause a nonuniform delamination growth along the specimen width and affect the observed initiation values [17]. A greater amount of scatter in toughness values was seen for samples containing hollow vascules, which may be a result of the variation in crack propagation paths discussed in section 3.3.

Figure 6 shows typical crack propagation routes for PTFE vascules. For the laminates with vascules, it can be seen that the crack remained between the central plies until it reached the first vascule, at which point it was arrested via crack blunting and then deflected to the corner of the resin pocket either after the first or the second vascule. The crack must propagate around the tube, thus debonding it from the matrix in the process, rather than breaking the boundary and passing through which is the case for the hollow vascules as seen by Norris et al [6]. On closer inspection of the fracture plane after experimental testing, the surfaces of all the PTFE vascules were partially exposed by the propagating crack, which will, in future studies, allow for the healing agent to permeate out. A small degree of fibre bridging was also observed, which is inherent in Mode I testing, and in some cases the crack did not remain in the same plane throughout the width of the specimen. The latter may be due to a number of factors such as inadequate consolidation in the laminate strips between each vascule or the load introduction being slightly misaligned.

Figure 6. Typical crack propagation paths for PTFE vascules

4 INTRODUCTION OF SELF-HEALING CAPABILITY

4.1. Methodology

To investigate the healing potential of the transverse vasculature embedded within Carbon SE70 a brief healing attempt was carried out on the fractured Mode I samples with hollow vasculature. RT151, a low viscosity epoxy resin (100cp) was used for these trials. The specimens were healed after initial fracture by delivering the RT151 self-healing agent externally via the first edge-located vasculature using 26 gauge hypodermic needles and left in an oven for 1 hour at 65°C. The healed specimens were then retested in Mode I DCB as outlined for the initial fracture, paying particular attention to the region between the end of the pre-crack and the first vasculature.

4.2. Results

The aim of this limited study was to first determine the potential and compatibility of this healing agent to heal the carbon SE70 specimens fractured under Mode I DCB, whilst also assessing the ease at which healing agent would spread over the fracture plane, excreting through pores. A similar trend to that which was observed for the initial fracture was seen, by which the vasculature acted to arrest the crack for a brief period of time. The fracture toughness of the healed laminate from the end of the pre-crack to just beyond the first vasculature was evaluated, and a comparison of the critical strain energy release rate at the point of the first vasculature between the initial fractured sample and a healed sample are displayed in figure 7. A fracture toughness recovery of 119% was attained, suggesting this may be a suitable resin system to impart healing functionality within this vascular laminate.

Figure 7. Comparison of the fracture toughness during the initial fracture and post-healing of the Mode I hollow vasculature samples as the crack arrives at the first vasculature

Figure 8 shows that on injection of the premixed healing agent into the vasculature, the crack plane thoroughly wet out. On retesting of the specimens under Mode I DCB, cohesive failure occurred, which was evident as the adhesive remained even on both the upper and lower surfaces of the crack plane.

Figure 8. Micrographs of the a) upper and b) lower fracture plane of the healed samples tested under Mode I propagation

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study confirmed the viability of incorporating a hollow thermoplastic fibre network into a fibre-reinforced composite with the potential for repeated self-healing. A fracture mechanics assessment of PTFE vasculature and a baseline laminate, under Mode I propagating cracks was undertaken and indicated adhesive failure occurred between the PTFE tubes and CFRP laminate, partially exposing the circumference of the tubes. Moderate crack arrest was observed at each vasculature in Mode I and the vasculature aided in slowing down the crack front, indicating the failure was a more progressive and controlled process than for the baseline.

These experiments indicate that inclusion of PTFE vasculature does not detrimentally affect the fracture toughness of the host laminate under Mode I crack propagation. Under normal loading conditions, cracks normally propagate as a combination of Mode I and Mode II conditions. Therefore in order to simulate more realistic fracture events, Mixed-Mode Bending (MMB) tests should be undertaken which would allow the experimenter to combine both Mode I and Mode II crack propagation under a predefined ratio. Further tests such as compression after impact (CAI) could also be considered in order to investigate the crack-vasculature interaction and possibility of self-healing, through the use of porous tubes, in different damage scenarios.

A low viscosity resin, RT151, was used to heal the crack plane in order to assess the compatibility of this resin with this material and network system. The resin spread over the crack plane well and the samples failed through cohesive failure. A healing efficiency of 119% was achieved signifying the potential of this system to offer healing functionality.

At present, the ability of the resin to flow through very small pores of a tube remains a key uncertainty. A microfluidics study of the volume flow rate of the healing agent through the pores on application of pressure should be carried out. Viscosity and surface friction of the tubes are important factors when considering microfluidics. Additionally, this study would ideally include an investigation into the effect of vasculature sizing and shape, spacing, wall thickness, pore sizing and shape, and number of pores, both around the circumference of the vasculature and along its length in order to find the optimal network design. Etching of small holes in PTFE tubing through a focused ion beam was

possible, however this method does not lend itself well to larger scale samples so other techniques will need to be explored.

As this study was considered as a ‘proof of concept’ study, only basic, small-scale experiments were carried out. In order to scale up to a more realistic, application-sized model, alternative manufacturing methods will eventually need to be considered, such as 3D printing or soft lithography. This will permit the introduction of branched networks and junctions into the composite on a much larger scale, introducing the potential for the healing agent to reach and heal larger damage volumes, possibly even through-thickness.

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